

EuroMix

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Specific recommendations regarding implementation of mechanism-based test strategy for harmonised cumulative risk assessment according OECD, WHO, EFSA and EuroMix Guidance

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Specific recommendations regarding implementation of mechanism-based test strategy for harmonised cumulative risk assessment according OECD, WHO, EFSA and EuroMix Guidance

Authors: Benjamin Fischer, Jens Schubert, Stefanie Rotter and Roland Solecki

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1. Introduction

The purpose of Task 9.2 was to summarise the key objectives and outcomes of the EuroMix WPs, to highlight the findings of Deliverable 9.1 as summarised in the position paper (Rotter, Beronius et al. 2019) and to briefly present the outcome of the four international harmonisation workshops as well as the WHO consultation in Geneva 2019. Building on those achievements, Task 9.2 aims to make recommendations addressing risk managers in the EU, i.e. EU Commission, regarding implementation of a harmonised assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals on the one hand and regulatory needs such as improved harmonisation between EFSA, SCoPAFF, OECD and WHO on the other.

The present report therefore aims to provide a very brief overview on the EuroMix project by highlighting the most relevant findings and summarising its conclusions for improvement of new guidance documents for risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals.

The report also considers the implementation of the recently published EFSA *Guidance on harmonized methodologies for human health, animal health and ecological risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals* (EFSA 2019), EFSA *Statement – Genotoxicity assessment of chemical mixtures* (EFSA 2019) as well as the OECD *Considerations for Assessing the Risks of Combined Exposure to Multiple Chemicals* with regard to future research and development needs (OECD 2018).

Further recommendations regarding the EuroMix toolbox are summarised in Deliverable 8.4 “Report with recommendation for OECD and other international organisations”.

2. EuroMix – summary of central objectives and outcomes

2.1. Objectives

The Horizon 2020 project “EuroMix” aims at contributing to the further development of internationally harmonized approaches and test strategies for risk assessments of chemical mixtures through an integrated test strategy involving *in vitro* and *in silico* tests for chemical mixtures.

Therefore, the main objective of EuroMix is the development of an experimentally validated, tiered strategy for the risk assessment of chemical mixtures, which can be derived from multiple sources. In detail, the approach comprises the following tasks:

1. Provide a refined grouping strategy for cumulative assessment groups using the component –based approach;
2. Development of a bioassay toolbox for mechanism-based grouping of chemicals into cumulative assessment groups;
3. Providing a strategy/establish criteria to set priorities for mixture assessment and testing (using quantitative structure-activity relation (QSAR) modelling);
4. Verification of the *in vitro* and *in silico* results for selected cumulative assessment groups;
5. Addressing *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation by using mathematical and physiologically-based pharmacokinetics/dynamics (PBPK/PBPD models);
6. Development of a web-based toolbox of models and data, to be used for cumulative and aggregate exposure, hazard and risk assessment;
7. Presenting case studies of aggregated and cumulative exposure, hazard and risk assessments, using the web-based toolbox for international implementation;
8. Development of criteria and guidance for testing mixtures in a tiered hazard and exposure modelling approach and to align the EuroMix innovation with key international organisations

- involved in cumulative and aggregative exposure and risk assessment, allowing harmonisation;
9. Providing an implementation strategy, training activities and workshops with stakeholders for dissemination.

2.2. Outcomes

The EuroMix methodology and toolbox is based on *in silico*, *in vitro* and *in vivo* tests in line with the OECD consideration (OECD 2018), the EFSA guidance (EFSA 2019) and reports from the EC Joint Research Centre (Bopp, Barouki et al. 2018). The EuroMix methodology supports addressing mixtures across regulatory sectors and can help in building capacities to better address mixtures and to set priorities for testing with regard to the identification and prioritisation of mixtures of high concern and to support stakeholders in saving resources.

In reference to the objectives, the achievements can be summed up as follows:

1. EuroMix delivers a web-based model and data platform (EuroMix toolbox, i.e. MCRA9) and provides a refined grouping strategy. Grouping can be done at different levels and according to the availability of data. The strategy has been implemented in the toolbox for cumulative assessment groups using the component-based approach; however, applying other criteria for grouping is possible as well. The EuroMix toolbox has also implemented an exposure driven approach as highlighted in the OECD document using the maximum cumulative ratio (MCR) and sparse non-negative matrix under approximation method (SNMU).
2. EuroMix delivers a bioassay toolbox for mechanism-based grouping of chemicals into cumulative assessment groups comprising, among others, *in vitro* testing of nuclear receptor activation, gene expression and protein expression.
3. EuroMix provides a strategy implemented in the toolbox (MCRA9) to set priorities for mixture assessment and testing (using *in silico* methods such as quantitative structure-activity relation (QSAR) modelling).
4. The applicability of *in vitro* and *in silico* results for selected cumulative assessment groups has been verified.
5. Extrapolation from *in vitro* to *in vivo* was implemented to derive relative potency factors (RPF) by using mathematical and physiologically-based pharmacokinetics/dynamics (PBPK/PBPD).
6. EuroMix delivers novel models to optimise exposure and hazard assessment and to substitute data in case of concentration or toxicological data gaps. The toolbox provides practical support to perform mixture risk assessment and testing of substances in line with recent OECD and EFSA guidance documents.
7. Case studies of aggregated and cumulative exposure have been published (Kennedy, Garthwaite et al. 2019) to promote further usage of the web-based toolbox and to contribute to international implementation of the toolbox.
8. Criteria for testing mixtures in a tiered hazard and exposure modelling approach have been developed. The criteria are implemented in the EuroMix toolbox (MCRA9) and described in the EuroMix handbook (Deliverable 8.3).
9. Training activities and workshops with stakeholders have been provided and additional training materials on how to use the testing concept and the EuroMix model and data platform will be published. Furthermore, templates and examples will be included in the handbook to facilitate the use of the concept and to enable stakeholders to gain experience and to collect data for future further developments.
10. Four international harmonisation workshops have been conducted to discuss current challenges and define necessary steps for the implementation of an internationally

harmonised, scientific approach to the risk assessment of combined exposures to chemicals .
The outcome is reported in Deliverable 9.3 available online¹.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/3479150#.XaB2AtL8Kpo>

2.3. Recommendations for further research and development needs concerning risk assessment of combined exposure identified within EuroMix

One major task within EuroMix was to review the current legislative requirements for risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals via multiple exposure routes, focusing on human health and particularly on food-related chemicals (Deliverable 9.1). The aim was to identify regulatory needs and current approaches for this type of risk assessment as well as challenges of the implementation of appropriate and harmonized guidance at international level. The following recommendations with regard to further research and development needs were highlighted in (Rotter, Beronius et al. 2019):

- Development of structured and flexible approaches and harmonized guidance for grouping chemicals into refined and relevant assessment groups;
- Establishing criteria for determining when substances have dissimilar Mode of Actions (MoAs)/Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) and deviate from the default assumption of dose addition;
- Development of guidance on how to apply an integrated testing and assessment strategy using alternative methodology and non-animal data, e.g. for strategies for refined grouping and for determining RPFs;
- Development of structured approaches for collecting data from exposure to multiple substances, either simultaneously or in sequence, for use in risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals;
- Development of guidance for analysing uncertainties associated with risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals, e.g. uncertainties associated with the grouping of chemicals into assessment groups and assumptions concerning similar MoAs/AOPs and application of dose addition.
- Integrate published data on toxicokinetics, AOPs, toxicological information and exposure modules into the EuroMix toolbox to improve the practicability and applicability.

Further recommendations and key actions were proposed by representatives of several EC funded research projects (EDC-MixRisk, EuroMix, EU-ToxRisk, HBM4EU, SOLUTIONS), aiming to better address combined effects and overcome remaining gaps in chemical mixture research (Altenburger, Barouki et al. 2018).

3. International organisations addressing assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals

3.1. European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

Guidance on harmonised methodologies for human health, animal health and ecological risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals EFSA (MIXTOX-Guidance)

Published: March 2019

The MIXTOX-Guidance describes the harmonised application of risk assessment methods for combined exposure to multiple chemicals. It does not solely focus on human health, but takes into account all relevant areas within EFSA remit, i.e. the aforementioned human health, as well as animal health and ecological areas (EFSA, 2019a). The aim is to present a flexible overarching framework for human health, animal health and ecological risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals. The harmonised framework refers to four steps of risk assessment, which, according to the document, are problem formulation, exposure assessment, hazard identification and characterisation, and risk characterisation.

Two approaches, the whole mixture as well as the component-based approach are taken into account for risk assessment of mixtures. In the first one, mixtures are treated as single entities, similar to single chemicals. To apply whole mixture approaches, data on toxicity of the whole mixture has to be available. Considering the possible number of mixtures, this is usually limiting the approach to assessments, in which there is direct exposure to the mixture by a single route of exposure. In case of a complex exposure pathway for a whole mixture, components tend to separate, possibly leading to the exposure of individuals to only a few components of the mixture, resulting in different hazard characteristics.

In component based approaches mixture risk assessment is based on exposure and effect data of its individual components. It was shown for both human/animal and an ecological effect, that prediction of toxicity of respective chemical mixtures is possible in cases, where the toxicity of the components is known for the endpoint of interest. Two models describing the toxicity of mixtures of substances are generally suggested to be used in this approach, dose addition and response addition. Prerequisite for applying the dose addition model is the assumption of common phenomenological effects of all substances in the mixture (assessment group), though their respective toxic potency might vary. The contribution of the mixtures single components to the effect is expressed by the ratio between their concentration and their toxic potency. Contrary to the dose addition model, base assumption for response addition is independent or dissimilar action of the mixtures components. It was shown “that both dose addition and, in fewer cases, response addition provide reasonable approximations for the prediction of combination effects, although deviations from predicted additivity, indicative of synergisms or antagonisms, exist and have been mainly reported in (eco)toxicological studies, they are rare and limited to specific chemical groups” (Boobis, Budinsky et al. 2011, Cedergreen and Nazir 2014).

Regardless of the model used for cumulative risk assessment, the guidance proposes a tiered approach. This allows using simple and conservative assumptions for hazard and exposure on lower tiers, which can be refined when the resulting risk metrics show potential risk or when more data becomes available. Tiering is not only useful for refining the assessment, but can also save resources by offering the possibility of discontinuing the analysis in case risk metrics indicate sufficient protection.

A key issue in cumulative risk assessment as described in this guidance is the grouping of substances into cumulative assessment groups (CAG). The guidance enables a flexible approach to the grouping

of chemicals, depending on problem formulation. Grouping of substances into CAGs can be based on co-occurrence or several commonalities, which can refer to legislation, exposure characteristics, physicochemical properties or hazard characteristics. Possible groups can be constituted by substances that share a regulatory domain, such as e.g. pesticides or by affecting the same organ, such as the liver. As more hazard data becomes available, risk assessors have the option to refine the grouping of chemicals using weight of evidence approaches, dosimetry (toxicokinetics) or mechanistic data such as MoA, AOP etc.

The final step is to summarise exposure and hazard metrics and to characterise the risk. In case of metrics indicating no unacceptable risk, there is no need for further action and the assessment can be terminated.

Recommendations extracted from the EFSA MIXTOX-Guidance

- Regardless of the model used for cumulative risk assessment, the guidance is recommending the application of a tiered approach, which should be specified in the problem formulation as a first important step.
- It is recommended that a component based approach might be more suitable in such cases, since it allows drawing conclusions regarding the effect of single components of mixtures which, in case of components indicating concern, allows regulating single substances instead of the whole mixture.
- It is recommended that variability of the mixture's composition in different exposure media should be taken into account by summing up the potency scaled exposures to the individual substances in the mixture.
- The toxicity of the mixtures of substances should be generally assessed by the two approaches, dose addition and response addition, respectively.
- The guidance strongly recommends a flexible approach to the grouping of chemicals, depending on problem formulation which can be based on co-occurrence or several commonalities or which can refer to legislation, exposure characteristics, physicochemical properties or hazard characteristics.
- Should metrics clearly indicate an unacceptable risk, risk management measures need to be implemented and the assessment needs to be continued on a higher tier using more accurate data, thus reducing uncertainty.

EFSA Statement – Genotoxicity assessment of chemical mixtures

Published: January 2019

The recently published EFSA statement on Genotoxicity assessment of chemical mixtures “primarily addresses specific issues related to hazard identification of genotoxicity of mixtures and provides a general framework for the assessment of genotoxic hazards of chemical mixtures”(EFSA 2019b).

The Scientific Committee differentiates between mixtures that are chemically fully defined or characterised and mixtures in which not all of the components have been characterised. Examples of characterised mixtures are mixtures that are produced by adding separate substances, well characterised mixtures produced by a controlled process or groups of separate substances to which combined exposure can occur (group of individual pesticides or food additives). It should be noted, that in this context “chemically fully defined” does not mean all components have to be known, even single substances are never 100% pure (impurities), but identities and relative ratios of components should be provided in the technical specification. The levels of impurities should not exceed the upper limit described in the technical specification.

State-of-the-art analytical techniques should be applied to detect and quantify impurities up to the limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ), based on the respective techniques used (e.g. GC-MS/MS, LC-MS/MS). For mixtures containing components that have not been chemically fully characterised, quantitative characterisation should be performed for the main constituents, which should cover at least sum parameters of e.g. total phenols. The percentage of unidentified components should be indicated and should be as low as possible.

The Scientific Committee addresses both component-based and whole mixture approaches that each are recommended according to the state of characterisation of the respective chemical mixture. Applying a component-based approach is recommended for chemically fully identified mixtures, i.e. all components are assessed individually, to avoid dilution of possible genotoxic effects, using all available information (read-across, QSAR). Therefore conclusions on genotoxicity will be required for all components or at least for representative chemical substances for mixtures containing structurally related substances.

In case of mixtures with a substantial proportion of chemically non-characterised substances, assessment of substances for their genotoxic potential, that are chemically defined, should be conducted first. Similar to fully characterised mixtures, each substance needs to be assessed individually in order to avoid dilution. If one or more substances in the mixture are evaluated *in vivo* to be genotoxic, then the whole mixture is considered to be genotoxic. Positive results *in vitro* are not sufficient to complete the assessment; additional *in vivo* data is needed. In cases where the chemically characterised substances do not raise concern of being genotoxic, the unidentified fractions genotoxic potential has to be evaluated, if possible. In cases where this is not feasible, scientific justification should be provided and testing of the whole mixture should be conducted. It might be necessary to further fractionate the test material prior to testing to reach adequately high doses by removing e.g. cytotoxic substances (EFSA 2019).

Recommendations extracted from the EFSA document

- Characterisation of mixtures as fully as possible.
- Demonstration of identity and stability of the mixture.
- Application of a component based approach for fully defined mixtures (assessment of substances individually).
- For non-fully defined mixtures, component based approach for the fully defined fractions and in case of negative results whole mixture approach for the unidentified fractions if feasible (otherwise whole mixture approach including the identified fractions).
- Similar to single substances, clearly negative results *in vitro* do not require further actions, whereas positive results need to be confirmed in follow-up *in vivo* testing.
- If positive results *in vitro* are not confirmed *in vivo*, uncertainties should be analysed, before concluding no genotoxic potential.
- Positive results for a single fraction raise concern for the whole mixture

3.2. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)

OECD CONSIDERATIONS FOR ASSESSING THE RISKS OF COMBINED EXPOSURE TO MULTIPLE CHEMICALS

Published: December 2018

Efforts were made by OECD member countries to expand the use of alternative, non-animal test strategies for the risk assessment of chemicals. Guidance documents have been developed to promote the use of those alternative methods such as Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship (QSAR), chemical categories and AOPs. The aim of the OECD document is to give an overview of the technical aspects of the various approaches and methodologies and at the same time to harmonize them to ensure consistency in how information is interpreted.

The OECD document was not intended to constitute strict guidance, but rather a collection of concepts that should be considered when assessing combined exposures to multiple chemicals. The OECD publication considers human and environmental risk assessment, however, in contrast to the EFSA guidance; it does not address animal health. Similarly to the EFSA guidance it recognises the fact that there are infinite numbers of chemical combinations to which humans and the environment can be exposed to and the importance to consider the impacts of combinations of these chemicals. It provides guidance for prioritising and scoping of combined exposures by taking into account the diversity of possible combinations, and the diversity of ways of prioritising their examination. It is also acknowledged that the application of different approaches and methods will depend on the assessment context and the problem formulation.

Recommendations extracted from the OECD document

- The central OECD concept is recommending that a tiered approach should be applied in order to identify where additional resources should be targeted for the refinement of assessment approaches, further data generation or gathering, or the consideration of risk management activities.
- The OECD underlined that there is a number of limitations and uncertainties associated with the various approaches, but this should be taken into consideration by risk managers and risk assessors.
- Since OECD also noted, that regulatory application of the approaches has not been extensive to date, it is pointed out that continued use of the methods and the identification of key gaps and uncertainties during the application will help build experience and refine methodologies moving forward. The EuroMix outcome including the toolbox could be very helpful to support this recommendation.
- The OECD's perspective supports the integration of novel tools and approaches into the regulatory decision-making process. International cooperation and coordination is considered as crucial for agreement on how novel methods can be used to refine, reduce and/or replace the testing of chemicals. Consequently, it is recommended that this should result in the best use of all available resources and avoid duplication of efforts.
- OECD considerations take into account several problem formulations, such as those highlighted in the EuroMix project. Additional mechanistic data (e.g. AOP) might reduce uncertainty; however, additional resources are necessary.
- As gaining experience requires additional case studies, policy decisions addressing and supporting those requirements are recommended.

3.3. World Health Organization (WHO)

FAO/WHO Expert Consultation on Dietary risk assessment of chemical mixtures (Risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals)

Published: April 2019

WHO conducted the “FAO/WHO expert consultation on dietary risk assessment of chemical mixtures” within the framework of the project EuroMix. Experts from EU and non-EU countries were invited to develop a guidance for the risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals on the international level. A report comprising a pragmatic approach to the risk assessment of combined exposures to multiple chemicals was published subsequent to the meeting (WHO, 2019) and is summarised in the following:

Several chemical groups have been established for substances such as e.g. organophosphates for risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals. If there is evidence, that substances being evaluated are sufficiently similar to substances included in an existing group, they should be regarded as part of that group and should be assessed together.

In case a substance is not included in an already established chemical group, it should be determined, if there is actual need to include that substance in a risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals.

To facilitate the decision of including a compound in a risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals, two metrics are proposed: health based guidance value (HBGV) and Margin of Exposure (MoE). Single compounds should be included, if the percentage of their estimated dietary exposure is greater than 10 percent of a HBGV relevant for the respective compound. If no HBGV was derived, decisions should be based on the MoE. In case the calculated MoE of a compound is less than 10 fold of a MoE regarded as being sufficient, inclusion in a risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals should be considered.

In case of substances, that are considered it should be clarified if there is toxicological evidence for combined effects of respective substances as well as possible synergisms between them.

It should further be clarified, if there is potential for co-exposure from either co-occurrence or internal exposure.

The contribution of chemicals to total dietary exposure should be taken into account “*when grouping chemicals into indicative assessment groups*”, especially in case of “*discontinued persistent pesticides that occur as contaminants (POPs)*” or dual use compounds (WHO, 2019). It is advised to follow established standard procedures to identify and characterise hazards, relative potency factors should be derived for chemicals in the assessment group, if feasible.

To estimate dietary exposure to multiple chemicals, “*a probabilistic approach is recommended, ideally using individual food consumption and concentration data*” (WHO, 2019). Use of deterministic methods may “*result in a higher level of uncertainty in the estimates, especially in the context of combined exposures to multiple chemicals*” (WHO, 2019). Physiologically based kinetic models can be applied for estimations of total internal exposures.

Risk characterisation is conducted using the dose addition approach. For identification of risk drivers, deterministic or probabilistic models may be used. The latter are available in several tools for single chemicals, however availability of tools for multiple chemicals is limited. A suitable tool was developed during the EuroMix project. Depending on results, refinement of assessment groups and revision of the risk assessment may be conducted.

The report of the meeting can be found on the WHO website (https://www.who.int/foodsafety/areas_work/chemical-risks/EUROMIX/en/).

Recommendations extracted from the FAO/WHO report (WHO, 2019):

- Development of a database with a simple list of parameters is required to systematically investigate potential assessment groups for consideration of combined exposures to multiple chemicals.
- Ensuring that databases of individual food consumption data for different countries (CIFOCOs and GIFT) and corresponding food concentration data are compatible so that dietary exposures and co-exposures can be undertaken in a consistent manner.
- Exploration of the use of summary reporting templates, for example, those from the EFSA MIXTOX-Guidance, to describe outcomes of the risk assessment for combined exposures of multiple chemicals in the final report.
- As a pilot exercise, JECFA 88 and JMPR 2019 should start identifying which compounds under evaluation should be considered for potential risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals in the future.
- The results of the pilot exercise using the proposed approach should be reviewed and the approach revised as appropriate, with particular consideration of the choice of decision point.
- Once agreed, the approach to risk assessment for combined exposure to chemical mixtures should be included in the updated FAO/WHO EHC240, in Chapter 6 Dietary exposure assessments and Chapter 7 Risk characterisation
- The standard JECFA/JMPR call for data process can include a request for completed risk assessments of combined exposure to multiple chemicals by other agencies to assist future evaluations.

3.4. Standing Committee on Plants, Animals, Food and Feed (SCoPAFF)

Both, Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 on maximum residue levels of pesticides (MRLs) and Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 on plant protection products contain the requirement to take into account known cumulative and synergistic effects where scientific methods are available. The Standing Committee – Section Pesticides Residues decided in 2013 to set up an electronic working group to discuss a proposed inventory of open questions for risk managers related to cumulative risk assessment of pesticide residues. The questions were prioritised and listed in chapter 3 of the “Working document on risk management aspects related to assessment of cumulative exposure” in descending order of priority. It was agreed to look at:

1. The retrospective scenario, focusing on the review of the monitoring data within a given period of time, thus referring to the post-authorisation period of an active substance
2. The prospective scenario, referring to the setting of MRLs following either an application for a new or existing active substance or a review of existing MRLs, thus mainly referring to the pre-authorisation period of an active substance, but also to its post-authorisation period in case of MRLs review

Under the DG RTD 7th FP funded project ACROPOLIS, coordinated by RIVM, the MCRA tool was developed and used in the project. The Commission gave a grant agreement to RIVM for the period 2015-2020 as a follow up project on the ACROPOLIS project to further improve the MCRA tool.

Within an agreement between EFSA and RIVM, RIVM has performed pilot cumulative exposure assessments of pesticide residues on effects on the nervous system and on chronic effects on the thyroid using the MCRA tool version 8.3. The assessments reflect the retrospective scenario of cumulative risk assessment and they were performed in accordance to the so far agreed open questions in the working document.

EFSA is finalising two pilot assessments of the cumulative effects of pesticide residues in food. These are retrospective assessments of the cumulative risks for the nervous system and the thyroid using monitoring data from 2014, 2015 and 2016 and are reported in the draft scientific reports on “Cumulative dietary risk characterisation of pesticides that have acute effects on the nervous system” (EFSA, 2019c; van Klaveren et al., 2019a) and “Cumulative dietary risk characterisation of pesticides that have chronic effects on the thyroid” (EFSA, 2019d; van Klaveren et al., 2019b). These assessments were conducted as the third step of a sequential process².

The first step was the establishment of cumulative assessment groups (CAGs) of pesticides for their effects on the nervous system (EFSA, 2019e) and the thyroid (EFSA, 2019f). For the second step, cumulative exposure assessments were conducted using probabilistic modelling with two different software tools. These pilot assessments represent an important step towards the inclusion of cumulative risk assessment in the annual reports on pesticide residues (article 32 of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005). They use methodologies not commonly used for the assessment of single substances such as probabilistic modelling, expert knowledge elicitation, uncertainty analysis and risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals.

During the EuroMix stakeholder meeting held on the 26th March 2019 the director for DG Sante announced that it is the intention to include cumulative risk assessment in a stepwise procedure. It is the intention to start in 2020 with the retrospective scenario using monitoring data and thereafter implement cumulative risk assessment in the MRL setting procedure.

² <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/consultations/call/public-consultation-draft-efsa-scientific-reports>

Recommendations extracted from the SCoPAFF Perspective

- Alignment of the MCRA programme to the requirements of the working document on cumulative risk assessment starting with the retrospective scenario followed by the prospective scenario (MRL setting procedure).
- Addressing the relevance of inclusion of pesticides in cumulative assessment group based on co-exposure and kinetic considerations.

4. EuroMix Recommendations

Over the last decade, it became obvious that risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals is complex and poses a number of challenges for scientists, risk assessors and managers. The prioritisation of this topic in policy and research has led to important debates and discussions between different organisations, authorities and institutions. Consequently first common principles and approaches have been defined for risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals. However, many challenges remain. In the following, recommendations for further development and research needs, implementation of existing tools and recommendations especially for risk managers are given.

1) Implementation of the EuroMix outcome into the European regulatory framework

- There is an urgent need for regulatory implementation of harmonized cumulative risk assessment according to OECD, WHO and EFSA guidance documents. EuroMix has taken steps to provide a methodology that is in line with the guidance documents provided by these organisations.
- A cross-cutting legal mandate for performing risk assessments of combined exposures to multiple chemicals is recommended to support an internationally harmonised practice.
- Risk managers need to set down rules on how to manage identified risks across different regulatory silos and to provide clear guidance on the acceptable degree of uncertainties.
- The EuroMix toolbox should be used in a follow-up to provide and, in cooperation with OECD, evaluate case studies and examples relevant in several regulatory silos.
- Risks that might result from the real co-exposure to multiple chemicals need to be assessed. The consideration of co-exposure of mixtures of concern based on exposure consideration, human biomonitoring and food surveillance data is recommended.
- Risk managers need to set down rules for problem formulation to conduct risk assessments of combined exposures to multiple chemicals in regard of responsibilities and necessary additional resources (personal and financial resources).
- A flexible approach to the grouping of chemicals based on hazard and exposure considerations in the problem formulation is strongly recommended. This should reflect co-occurrence or several commonalities or can refer to legislation, exposure characteristics, physicochemical properties or hazard characteristics.

2) Ensuring the accessibility and transparency of the tools developed in the EuroMix project

- The EuroMix toolbox (MCRA9) runs on high performance computing facilities currently hosted by RIVM. However model calculations are complex and thus costly. Computational time has to be paid by the institutes using MCRA9 in the future. Therefore, risk managers need to provide sufficient financial resources to further operate the EuroMix toolbox and to provide access to all relevant stakeholders.
- The possibility to trace back input parameters should be further implemented in the toolbox in a follow-up project, in order to increase the transparency of regulatory decisions.
- Risk managers should set-up data sharing agreements which enable to use data in the toolbox to:
 - encourage data sharing in general without granting full access (i.e. no download of data)
 - improve and encourage sharing of residue and consumption data in the EuroMix toolbox between member states and other stakeholders.

- produce additional and especially structured data in a follow-up project, preferably using *in vitro* assays, to support adverse outcome pathways based grouping (i.e. grouping of substances with common endpoints, verified by *in vitro* assays).

3) Further development of the methods used in the EuroMix project for the assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals

- The EuroMix project provides first results for the application in regulatory frameworks and agreement as well as support for further research. However, improvement and refinement of some modelling approaches (e.g. *in silico* modelling, kinetic modelling, multiple route exposure modelling) is still necessary.
- The necessary development of alternative regulatory strategies for the assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals needs to identify optimal *in vitro* models and to define a screening tool box for regulatory purposes.
- Development and validation of OECD test guidelines for *in vitro* and *in silico* methods that are suitable for the assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals is necessary to safeguard their regulatory acceptance.

4) Further promotion of cooperation and strengthen existing networks in the field of the assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals

- Set up a network involving European and Non-European authorities and international organisations such as EFSA, WHO and US-EPA to generate synergies and bundle forces to develop a harmonised approach for the evaluation of mixtures. The network should:
 - Compile available data on mixture toxicity and case studies in publicly accessible databases to support science and decisions of risk assessors
 - Verify *in silico* methods and *in vitro* bioassays and the extrapolation of these results to humans.
 - Clarify if a general, systematic and comprehensive framework is feasible for both the protection of human and environmental health
- EFSA should be encouraged to use the EuroMix toolbox, in combination with the MIXTOX-Guidance, and also to integrate other available EU tools.
- Further training of relevant stakeholders in using the toolbox is recommended to assure the correct use and outcome of the EuroMix toolbox.

5) Safeguard visibility and dissemination of the results of the EuroMix projects to further promote cumulative risk assessment

- Establishment and maintenance of an open access database containing the relevant publications in the field of the assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals.
- Regarding future research and development needs, it is recommended to organise two meetings a year with risk managers, risk assessors and stakeholders to synchronise the work and to agree on new developments, new endpoints to address in the test strategy and refinement in mixture risk assessment by exposure considerations rather than hazard considerations only.

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